

GUIDE PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining dasrlarda ijodiy faoliyatga qiziqtirish, yo'llash uslublari bo'yicha batafsil ma'lumot bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, dars faoliyatini olib boorish bo'yicha metodik tavsiyalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, ijodiy faoliyat, metodika, o'quvchi va o'qituvchi, ko'nikma va uslublar.

Annotation: This article provides detailed information on methods of getting primary school students interested in creative activities in the classroom. Also, methodical recommendations for conducting lesson activities are described.

Key words: primary education, creative activity, methodology, student and teacher, skills and methods.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о методах привлечения учащихся начальных классов к творческой деятельности на уроке. Также описаны методические рекомендации по проведению уроков.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, творческая деятельность, методика, ученик и учитель, умения и методы.

In primary education, in addition to heuristic and problem-based education, it is advisable to use scientifically based educational methods and games in the development of students' creative activities. In primary education, the use of role-playing, plot games is of great importance. In the development of creative activity,

the use of forms and methods of organizing scientific activity related to knowledge, which leads to creative ability, scientific and creative research, has given its results. In this regard, classes for the development of creative activity include dialogue classes, discussions, debates, conversations, fantasy, research classes, classes for setting problems and solving them; Participatory classes, modeling, artistic and technical creativity, creativity, creating small discoveries, writing essays, making chronicles, using business games, innovative methods, etc., were the most effective, as game methods of lesson forms in the educational process certain of the teaching will be held during

It is known that elementary school students are interested in imitating the behavior of adults. In this case, the use of business games used in the educational process is very important. Business games for children are held in order to repeat, consolidate, and determine the level of learning of what has been learned (dictations, competitions, crosswords, field trips in the form of role-playing games, dramatic scenes).

Organization of business games on the basis of simulation and modeling of life tasks leads to effective results. Such games are characterized not only by knowledge, but also by broadening the worldview and emotional impact. For example, in primary education, when using innovative methods such as "Why?", "T-chart", "FSMU", "Network (Cluster)", "Two-part diary", it directly helps to develop creative activity in students. In scientific and methodical literature, we still meet terms such as "creativity", "creativity". It is not for nothing that these terms appeared in the pages of literature. The dictionary meaning of the word "creativity" is similar to the words "to create", "to discover something new".

Creativity appears in various situations of activity. Curiosity includes the process of inspiration, aspiration, etc., from the emergence and manifestation of

creativity in the human mind in the highest way. The need for activity in a person is an aspiration that has not been previously set as a goal in the activity, and is not considered a solution tool. Creativity is the process of human activity that creates qualitatively new, material and spiritual wealth. Creativity represents the ability of a person manifested in work. Work can be creative as it creates a new reality that satisfies various social needs based on knowledge of the laws of the objective world. Types of creativity are determined by creative activity: inventor, organizer, scientific and artistic work, etc. Opportunities for creative activity depend on social relations. Today, the educational reforms carried out due to independence depend on the training of highly qualified personnel who have a creative approach to their work and contribute to the rapid development of science, technology, art, and production. Accordingly, it is important and necessary to educate every student in the spirit of creativity, based on the students of social development.

Psychologist and scientist N.D. Levitov proved that creative activity is created based on the following criteria:

- independence of thinking;
- assimilation, speed and consistency of educational material;
- the ability to think (ingenuity) when solving non-standard tasks speed;
- by going deep into the essence of the phenomena being studied to be able to distinguish the important from the unimportant.

In primary education, the conditions for the formation of students' creative activity are first understood as the process of emergence, implementation and development of these conditions. They consist of:

1. The acquisition of students in this regard in the formation of their creative activity

necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications.

2. Theoretical knowledge and practice in the formation of creative activity relatedness.
3. Training on the formation of creative activity, heuristics are problematic create situations.
4. Technological approach to the formation of students' creative activity.

These conditions apply as follows:

The following requirements are set for the knowledge, skills, and abilities that students should acquire when forming their creative activities.

- the extent to which the program has mastered the materials;
 - mastering the basic concepts and rules of the subjects;
 - able to independently complete assignments on the chosen topic;
- understand the main problems in the studied topics;
- educational materials and technical tools, information for completing assignments
- able to use technology;
- to show his ability and be able to develop it;
 - able to set achievable goals and make plans and be able to evaluate results;
 - being able to prove his opinion when studying topics;
 - being able to recommend one's own option, etc.

These requirements for the teacher are the students' interest in learning, there is an opportunity to know their educational activity, individual inclinations, and in this regard, it helps to determine the structure of the educational process. On the basis of the above requirements, the priority directions for the purposeful organization of education related to the problem are determined. The purposeful

approach is a specially organized goal-oriented approach to the development of creative activity of the educational process or educational content, methods and forms of the system. structure is understood.

One of the main tasks of pedagogy is to create conditions that ensure the comprehensive development of creative activity of all children. In addition, it is necessary to identify students who show deep interest, desire and ability in certain fields, and to create all opportunities for their further development. For this, it is important to create conditions for the development of creative activities of students of primary school age. In this regard:

1. Innovative activities related to the development of students' creative activities preparation
2. Creating cooperation between teachers and students.
3. Innovative technologies for knowledge in the development of creative activity use.

In the current period, heuristic and problem-based education, which is related to the independent search and discovery of a truth by students, is actively entering the learning process. V. In her research, Karimova identified the following three types of scientific activity:

- 1) Necessary in the process of observing the external world by students qualities;
- 2) Conditions for creating a creative product of activity for students qualities of creative activity that provide;
- 3) When students organize cognitive activity in its previous two states - cognition and shows that its visible qualities are manifested in the state of creation.

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